

BUCKLING AND POST-BUCKLING IN FILAMENT WOUND COMPOSITE TUBES UNDER TRANSVERSE COMPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

Transverse compression (ring deflection) tests were simulated in composite tubes through nonlinear finite element models based on a modified Riks algorithm, which uses the arc-length method. Progressive failure was evaluated in detail through a proposed damage model, able to identify the failure mode. In all composite tubes tested, localized stress concentration points developed in the transverse plane caused by contact load plates/composite, producing non-linearity in the load vs. displacement curves ($P-\delta$). The failure mode of these tubes involves a complex combination of mechanisms, namely transverse tensile, transverse compression and in-plane shear stresses, where the region of the specimen in contact with the load plates present the most damaged area. Thus, matrix tensile and matrix compression induced by shear near the loading zones dominate damage and failure of the specimens. Buckling and post-buckling of tubes are highly influenced by the fiber orientation, whereas the tube with reinforcement orientation parallel to the loading plates-to-specimens contact line withstanding the highest buckling load level. On the other hand, specimens wound at $[\pm 45]_5$ and $[\pm 75]_5$ present a divergence point, since they support a portion of the load after buckling is reached, characterizing a post-buckling behavior.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cylindrical shells have numerous applications in aerospace, aeronautic and marine structures, such as in launch vehicle fuel tanks, fuselages and offshore structures. They have the ability to carry high levels of axial and transverse compression, since most of the structure is loaded in a membrane state and its efficiency is derived from the lack of through-the-thickness stress gradients [1]. These structures are traditionally metallic-based, therefore due to the ever-growing need to decrease the payload in such aeronautic and marine structures, the use of polymeric composites is being motivated, mainly due to their high corrosion resistance and high stiffness- and strength-to-weight ratios.

Filament winding (FW) process stands out in composite materials processing because of its high precision in fiber positioning, high fiber content, high automation capability and low void content. Due to these characteristics, FW is the most common process for manufacturing revolution and axisymmetric parts, such as composite overwrapped pressure vessels and tubes. When these structures

act under uniaxial or biaxial load, as the load increases steadily, the shell starts to deform stably. When the load achieves a critical point, the equilibrium stops and instability may be set. Thus, buckling occurs when the structure suddenly deflects unstably and loses its capacity to keep resisting the compressive loading. Fig. 1 shows a typical load vs. displacement response for an unstable problem.

Composite tubes with a sufficiently thin-wall shell fail due to either global or local buckling when under an instable loading, and they have two possible distinct characteristics: the first one is that the development of significant radial and/or axial displacements is followed by the development of global buckling phenomena and a consequently collapse; and the second one is that the prediction of the load level at which collapse occurs is difficult when compared to well-behaved structures, such as beams and plates [1,2].

Figure 1: Typical response of a structure under unstable loading [3].

It is common to find researches dealing with isotropic and even composite tubes under axial compression [4,5,6], which is the most classical case of a structure under an instable loading that causes buckling. However, there are no reports about the buckling behavior of composite cylindrical shells under transverse compression, which can be relevant for tubes acting under either transverse compression or hydrostatic external pressure. In both cases, the structure can fail by buckling or material failure, where they are strongly dependent of the stacking sequence, wall thickness, boundary conditions or geometrical imperfections [7].

In some cases, the structure can support a portion of the applied loading after buckling is reached, formerly known as post-buckling, typical of isotropic metallic structures. However, a composite structure may also present a post-buckling behavior even with its brittle fracture behavior. For instance, White et al. [1] performed the post-buckling analysis of variable-stiffness cylindrical shells under axial compression through linear and non-linear analysis, where both presented results within the error range achieved in experimental results, but the non-linear analysis predicted better the final post-buckled shape. Tafreshi [2] developed a numerical model to predict the buckling and post-buckling behavior of composite cylinders under external pressure and axial compression, where the delamination was the main cause of the buckling. Harte and Fleck [8] investigated the failure behavior of braided composite cylinders under axial compression and torsion, where different failure modes were successfully predicted in the developed models.

In this context, this work deals with the development of reliable models to represent the buckling and post-buckling behavior of composite tubes under transverse compression (also referred to as ring deflection). Two strategies have been implemented: i) geometrically non-linear analyses and ii) advanced damage modelling.

2 BASICS OF BUCKLING

2.1 Linear buckling analysis

Firstly, a linear Eigenvalue buckling analysis was carried out aiming at determining the buckling

critical load and the deformed shape for the composite tubes under transverse compression. The essence of an eigenvalue buckling problem is to find the loads where the stiffness matrix becomes singular, and thus the problem has non-trivial solutions [9], being represented by Eq. 1:

$$K^{mn}v^m = 0 \quad (1)$$

where K^{mn} is the tangent stiffness matrix when the load is applied and v^m are non-trivial displacement solutions.

In the linear buckling analysis, a perturbation is applied to the undeformed shape of the specimen. Specified sets of loadings are monitored for which deflections could induce instability when under a geometric non-linearity (also known as P-Delta, P- δ , effect), which involves the equilibrium and compatibility relationships of a structural system loaded about its deflected configuration [3]. Linear buckling procedure generates a range of buckling factors and corresponding mode shapes. When loading is multiplied by these buckling factors, the resulting scaled loading conditions represent those that induce buckling. Similarly, the mode shapes are normalized displacement sets which indicate the configuration of the buckled structure [10,11].

2.2 Non-linear buckling and post-buckling analysis

In order to evaluate both buckling and post-buckling of the structure, a non-linear buckling model is suitable to provide more accurate results than the elastic formulation. In this analysis, an applied loading incrementally increases until a large change in displacement occurs for a certain increment. This condition typically points that the structure has become unstable. Non-linear buckling analysis is a static method that accounts for material and geometric non-linearity, load perturbations and/or geometric imperfections. Geometrically non-linear static problems occasionally involve buckling or collapse behavior, where the load-displacement response displays a negative stiffness and the structure should release strain energy to remain in equilibrium [2].

Buckling analysis commonly provides a bifurcation after the structure loses its equilibrium, but even in snap-through problems (equilibrium path in load-displacement space is smoothed and does not branch) the Riks algorithm may be employed. In case of a snap-through behavior, the structure can carry increasing load after a complete snap [12].

3 MATERIAL MODEL

This material model was originally developed by Ribeiro et al. [7] at a mesoscale approach, where it was adapted to the material and geometry herein used. The model regards to the composite lamina under plane stress state and the damage is considered uniform throughout the laminate thickness [13].

3.1 Fiber modelling

A unidirectional carbon/epoxy composite laminate under tensile loading in the fiber direction (σ_{11}) is linear elastic with brittle fracture. Thus, for tensile load in fiber direction, the maximum stress criterion is used to identify the fiber failure:

$$\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_t} \leq 1 \quad (1)$$

After failure is reached, the damage variable in fiber direction (d_1) is set to “0.99”. There is no evolution of d_1 aiming at represent the catastrophic failure of the carbon fiber. To avoid possible localization issues, the degradation of properties is calculated in the step “ i ”, however it is applied into the step “ $i + 1$ ”, thus improving the convergence process.

The fiber behavior under compressive longitudinal load is set to be linear elastic until a specified value, after that, a non-linear elastic behavior is observed. The linear elastic to non-linear elastic limit (X_{C0}) is then used in Eq. 2 to represent the compressive failure, as follows:

$$\frac{|\sigma_{11}|}{X_{C0}} \leq 1 \quad (2)$$

After $|\sigma_{11}| \geq X_{C0}$ any increase in the compression loads in fiber direction results in a non-linear

elastic stress–strain behavior. This non-linear elastic behavior is simulated using a secant modulus as can be seen in Eq. 3:

$$E_{11} = \frac{X_{c0}}{|\varepsilon_{11}|} (1 - h(\varepsilon_{11})) + h(\varepsilon_{11})E_{11_0} \quad (3)$$

Where $h(\varepsilon_{11})$ is obtained from the fit of stress-strain plots for 0° specimens under compressive loading, ε_{11} is the strain in longitudinal direction and E_{11_0} is the initial elastic modulus from 0° specimens under compression loading.

3.2 Matrix modelling

In a unidirectional quasi-flat filament wound laminate, the damage process in the matrix is essentially dominated by the transverse loading (σ_{22}) and shear loading (τ_{12}). A non-linear behavior in the matrix is reported due to inelastic strains and damage in matrix [14]. To model the damage process in matrix, two internal damage variables, d_2 (related to σ_{22}) and d_6 (related to τ_{12}), were used. Based on Continuous Damage Mechanics, the hypothesis of effective stress links the damage variables to the stresses [9], and Eq. 4 gives the relationship

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \hat{\sigma}_{11} \\ \hat{\sigma}_{22} \\ \hat{\tau}_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/1 - d_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1/1 - d_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1/1 - d_6 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \tau_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where $\hat{\sigma}_{ij}$, $\hat{\tau}_{ij}$ are the second order effective stress tensors.

According to Herakovich [9], the damage strain energy density can be described in function of effective stresses considering only for matrix phase stresses, as shows Eq. (5)

$$E_D = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\langle \sigma_{22}^2 \rangle_+}{E_{22_0}(1-d_2)} + \frac{\langle \sigma_{22}^2 \rangle_-}{E_{22_0}} + \frac{|\tau_{12}^2|}{G_{12_0}(1-d_6)} \right] \quad (5)$$

where $\langle \sigma_{22}^2 \rangle_+ = \sigma_{22}^2$ if $\sigma_{22} > 0$, otherwise $\langle \sigma_{22}^2 \rangle_+ = 0$ if $\sigma_{22} < 0$. Similarly, $\langle \sigma_{22}^2 \rangle_- = -\sigma_{22}^2$ if $\sigma_{22} < 0$, otherwise $\langle \sigma_{22}^2 \rangle_- = 0$ if $\sigma_{22} > 0$.

Another aspect of the present model must be highlighted, which consists in an adjustment of the Poisson's coefficient for consider the damage effect. Using CDM formulation performed by Matzenmiller et al. [15], Eq. 8 gives the compliance tensor:

$$D = \frac{1}{K} \begin{bmatrix} (1 - d_1)E_{11} & (1 - d_1)(1 - d_2)v_{21}E_{22} & 0 \\ (1 - d_1)(1 - d_2)v_{12}E_{11} & (1 - d_2)E_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & K(1 - d_6)G_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where, $K = (1 - (1 - d_1)(1 - d_2)v_{12}v_{21})$. Aiming at avoiding the material self-healing, the damage parameters (d_1 , d_2 e d_6) are assumed as the maximum "0.99" along the simulation [7].

4 FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

The herein presented models were built up in Abaqus™ 6.14 software platform.

The original dimensions of the tubes are: length (l) = 381 mm, radius (r) = 68 mm and lamina thickness (t_l) \approx 0.6 mm (t_l varies according to winding angle). The structure was modeled with S4R shell elements with three integration points in each layer. The cylindrical shell has been submitted to a transverse compressive load by contact from the compression plates (rigid bodies). Fig. 3 depicts the assembly of the virtual test.

The tubes were modelled by using four node reduced integration shell element (S4R) with hourglass control. Table 1 presents the comprehensive material properties of the carbon/epoxy laminates. A compressive load was applied into the top compressive plate (rigid body) and the other plate is clamped. The buckling loading was transmitted to the specimen by contact from the rigid bodies. A modified Riks algorithm based on the arc-length method was used to predict is buckling and/or post-buckling occurs. Figure 2 presents the assembly of the virtual test.

<i>Elastic constants</i>	E_1 (GPa)	129.3
	$E_2 = E_3$ (GPa)	9.11
	$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	0.32
	ν_{23}	0.35
	$G_{12} = G_{13}$ (GPa)	5.44
	G_{23} (GPa)	2.10
<i>Strengths</i>	X_t (MPa)	1409.9
	X_c (MPa)	-740.0
	Y_t (MPa)	42.5
	Y_c (MPa)	-140.3
	S_{12} (MPa)	68.9

Table 1: Material properties used as input in the numerical models.

Figure 2: Assembly of the transverse compression test.

4.1 Parametric study

A parametric study was carried out aiming at evaluate the mechanical response of the tube with different winding sequence and radius/thickness (r/t) ratios. Table 1 shows all configurations used in the simulations.

<i>Specimen code</i>	<i>Stacking sequence</i>	<i>r/t ratio</i>
$[\pm 45]_5$	$[\pm 45]_5$	22.7
$[\pm 75]_5$	$[\pm 75]_5$	
$[\pm 90]_5$	$[90]_5$	
$r/t_{22.7}$	$[90]_5$	22.7
$r/t_{28.3}$	$[90]_4$	28.3
$r/t_{37.7}$	$[90]_3$	37.7

Table 2: Description of all specimen configurations used for the parametric study.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 3 presents the linear-elastic simulations to identify the global mechanical response of the tubes with different winding angles under transverse compression. The tube wound with hoop layers ($[90]_5$) supports higher compressive load than the other layups simulated. This performance was foreseen since the composite tube is loaded in fiber (hoop) direction. Even with geometric nonlinearity activated in the model, it is obvious that no buckling happens, where all specimens supported the

applied load until the maximum displacement set.

Figure 3: Load \times displacement curves for the three winding angle evaluated through a non-linear elastic analysis with geometric nonlinearity activated.

Figure 4 shows the load proportionality factor (LPF) vs. total arc length of the simulations through a nodal analysis, aiming at finding the bifurcation point and critical buckling load for the tubes analyzed. In these plots, the values are not relevant, however the curve shape reveals the geometrical instability throughout the analysis. As can be noted, the fiber orientation influences directly on the compressive behavior of composite tubes, since the specimen $[90]_5$ present a clear buckling load without evidence of post-buckling, considering that when the structure buckles the analysis converges to a unique solution, a failure by buckling. On the other hand, the specimens $[\pm 45]_5$ and $[\pm 75]_5$ do not present a clear buckling load, but it is possible to find a bifurcation point due to the non-linear shape of the curves.

Figure 4: Load proportionality factor vs. arc length obtained from the nodal analysis for identify the buckling load and bifurcation point.

Figure 5 may complement previous results obtained from Figure 4, showing the load vs. displacement plots for the cylinders. Specimen $[\pm 45]_5$ presents a slightly drop at around 20 kN with a displacement of 40 mm, which can be find as a bifurcation point, to be confirmed by analyzing the material failure. The cylinder wound at $[\pm 75]_5$ is the sequence that presents less influence of buckling,

since the cylinder start to behave slightly unstable after a displacement of 30 mm. The specimen $[90]_5$ loses its structural integrity at 44.7 kN, being that the buckling load.

Figure 5: Load × displacement profile curves for the tubes with different winding angle through a nodal analysis.

Analyzing the shape of the cylinders in an increment that the structure starts to lose structural stability (Figure 6), it is clear that the tubes are too dependent of the fiber orientation, since the hoop wound tube presents a typical mode I of buckling under a compressive load. However, it cannot be stated that any of these structures may failed buckling. For that, a failure evaluation seems crucial to understand the complete behavior of these structures under an unstable load.

Figure 6: Deformed shape of the tubes at the increment in which the structure starts to be unstable.

5.1 Failure and damage analysis

Figure 7 presents the progressive failure analysis for the tubes exhibited through the load vs. displacement curves. As can be noted, the tube $[90]_5$ presented a sudden failure at ≈ 25 kN with a displacement 20.7 mm. Although Riks analysis pointed a buckling load of ≈ 44.7 kN, the failure analysis evidences that the tube fails by material failure before achieve the buckling load. The specimen $[\pm 45]_5$ has a bifurcation point at a load of 18.1 kN at the displacement of 38.2 mm, which is similar to buckling load found at the nodal analysis. This curve shape suggests a post-buckling behavior, since the specimen does not fail at the buckling load, since the structure keep carrying a portion of the compressive load. The tube $[\pm 75]_5$ points a bifurcation at a load of 24.5 kN and displacement of 35.7 mm, but with a large amount of failed plies, characterizing that the structure post-buckles but with various plies damaged.

It is interesting to observed in these load vs. displacement profiles that the curves fluctuate along the analysis with several tiny discontinuities, which may correspond to progressive failure of the plies. A typical issue in these test is the contact between the rigid plates and the composite specimen, since

this contact may induce a transverse shear between them, being cause a premature failure of the specimen.

Figure 7: Mechanical response of the tubes simulated by using the damage model herein proposed.

It is observed a high dependence of the winding angle on the failure of the specimens under the compressive load. As the winding angle increases, the failure load increases. The analysis indicate that when the fiber orientation is aligned perpendicular to the loading axis, the cylinder become more stable under transversal compressive loading. Thus, with fibers wound in the hoop direction, the tube is more able to sustain higher hoop stress levels prior to failure.

5.2 Parametric study

Figure 7 shows typical curves for the tube $[90]_5$ with different radius-to-thickness (r/t) ratios. As the r/t ratio increase, the buckling load decreases, once as thinner as the wall thickness the structure becomes more susceptible to buckling. In addition, as higher as the r/t ratio, the specimen displace more at a lower maximum peak load. The specimen $r/t_{37.7}$ has the most instability throughout the analysis, which can be attributed to the high influence of transverse shear stresses. Despite at different loads, a similar profile is observed for each tube until ≈ 20 mm, presenting a linear response. The deviation from linearity to non-linearity is clear for all specimens, even though at different load stages indicating active damage mechanisms in all tubes.

Figure 8: Mechanical response for the cylinders with several radius-to-thickness ratios.

The deformed shape of these tubes at the failure load is shown in Figure 9, where the thinnest tube present a bifurcation point at a load of 7.8 kN and a displacement of 25 mm, being this the reason for a high displacement by supporting a small portion of the load (compared to the other tubes). This cylinder has a matrix-dominated failure mode, mainly by transverse shear and transverse tensile stresses. It is valid to mention the stress concentrations created at the contact plate/specimen, however this cylinder does not present fiber-dominated failure.

Figure 9: Final deformed shape of each tube and their spatial displacement in the circumferential direction.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The scope of this paper was to evaluate the buckling and/or post-buckling response of filament wound composite tubes under a transversal compressive load. For that, a non-linear analysis based on a modified arc-length method was used to predict the buckling load and the bifurcation point. In addition, a damage model was proposed, in order to understand the progressive failure and damage upon buckling onset of the tubes with several winding angle and radius-to-thickness ratio.

The specimen wound with hoop layers supported the highest compressive load, pointing a buckling load of about 40 kN, whereas the tubes $[\pm 45]_5$ and $[\pm 75]_5$ have a bifurcation point in lower loads, presenting a post-buckling behavior, since the structure still support portion of the load of buckling is reached. However, the specimen $[90]_5$ failed in the material before a buckling load, with a combination of transverse tensile, in-plane shear and radial compression, beyond a few fiber-dominated failures at the contact between the rigid plates and composite specimen, being this point the final failure location. The failure analysis corroborated that the $[\pm 45]_5$ and $[\pm 75]_5$ present post-buckling after a displacement at around 40 mm, and the tube $[90]_5$ did not show post-buckling.

The next step of this research is to carry out the experiments to validate the buckling and post-buckling models herein developed, as well as the damage model and progressive failure of the plies during this test.

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